

From Classroom to the Industry: PBL in Action from the point of view of a team of students

Ana Carolina Cunha¹, Ana Catarina Abreu¹, Ana Luísa Machado¹, Bárbara Silva¹, Carolina Dantas¹, Catarina Wilson¹, Inês Araújo¹, Lara Correia¹, Raquel Dantas¹, Rui M. Lima¹

¹ ALGORITMI Centre, Department of Production and Systems, School of Engineering, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal

Email: carolinacunha423@gmail.com, catarinarmabreu@gmail.com, aluisadsm@gmail.com, barbarasilva220203@gmail.com, carolinadantas8@gmail.com, catarina.gomes.wilson@gmail.com, inesaraujo422@gmail.com, larafranciscacccc@gmail.com, dantasraquel2002@gmail.com, rml@dps.uminho.pt

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15881509>

Abstract

Active learning encourages students to actively engage in the classroom rather than passively receiving information from lectures. Over the past decade, universities have increasingly adopted active learning, proving its effectiveness in enhancing student outcomes. In the Master's Degree in Industrial Engineering and Management at the University of Minho, students are encouraged to work in collaborative groups to solve real complex problems. This approach is implemented in the Integrated Project in Industrial Engineering and Management course, which implements Project-Based Learning (PBL). Through PBL, students engage directly with companies to address real-world challenges, fostering University-Business Cooperation. This methodology provides an exceptional opportunity for engineering students to develop critical competences demanded by the professional world, including project management competences, bridging the gap between the learning process and industry practice. Moreover, the opportunity arose to integrate the project into an international and more sustainable dimension through the ERASMUS+ EGALITARIAN project, aiming to raise awareness within the company about its environmental footprint. The main objective of this article is to characterise the development of competences and the application of knowledge acquired throughout the academic journey, from the eyes of a team of students developing the project. Moreover, the article aims to describe the agile project management approach implemented by this team, which may be a valuable example for other students working in PBL. The experience proved to be highly enriching, offering students the opportunity to strengthen critical competences such as problem-solving, teamwork and project management. Additionally, participants enhanced their ability to communicate effectively with stakeholders, think critically under pressure and adapt to industrial challenges, while also developing valuable competences in areas such as sustainability assessment and environmental impact analysis. As part of the ERASMUS+ EGALITARIAN program, the project combined cross-cultural collaboration focusing on sustainable practices and fostering environmental responsibility among future leaders in engineering and management.

Keywords: Project-Based Learning; University-Business Cooperation; Industrial Engineering and Management.

1 Introduction

Active learning methods have proven to be effective in improving engineering self-efficacy, academic performance and students' sense of responsibility in completing future tasks (Major & Kirn, 2017). These learning approaches include problem-based learning (PBL), case studies, group projects, simulations and other collaborative activities that encourage students to take an active role in their learning (Jaroenkhasemmesuk et al., 2023). Within this framework, PBL enables students to develop competencies by engaging in project work that addresses real-world problems (Lima et al., 2017).

Furthermore, research indicates that active learning approaches, such as PBL, are significantly more effective (Freeman et al., 2014; Theobald et al., 2020) than traditional direct instruction in promoting student learning outcomes. Notably, PBL has been shown to enhance students' engineering self-efficacy, a factor strongly correlated with student performance in engineering education. If similar results are observed for engineering design self-efficacy and PBL, it is expected that students' willingness to engage in learning and design activities

will increase through the implementation of active learning strategies into engineering programs (Major & Kirn, 2016).

The development of projects in industrial context constitutes an exceptional opportunity for engineering students to develop competences expected by the labour market (Lima et al., 2017).

According to Alves et al. (2016), teachers have identified PBL as a positive learning approach that enhances student motivation, engagement and comprehension of the practical applications of theoretical concepts. Additionally, research has explored the role of teachers and their perceptions of PBL (Habók & Nagy, 2016; Han et al., 2015) and shows that integrating them into a university-industry collaboration framework offers further advantages in addition to the benefits of active learning methods. Students demonstrate higher levels of engagement and motivation when working on real-world problems proposed by companies. Additionally, this approach creates an enriched learning environment that closely simulates the conditions and challenges they will encounter in their professional careers (Jaca et al., 2021). However, there is a lack of studies examining PBL from the students' perspective.

This study was conducted at University of Minho, a public university in northern Portugal, with first-year Master's students in Industrial Management and Engineering during the first semester of the 2024/2025 academic year. It took place within a project-based course that adopts an interdisciplinary PBL approach in collaboration with industrial companies. Furthermore, some students took part in ERASMUS+ EGALITARIAN project, a student-led initiative that unites individuals from diverse backgrounds to develop innovative solutions for improving waste management and supporting waste pickers in Brasília, in line with the goals of the 2030 Agenda. Each semester, the initiative fosters new projects aimed at creating a meaningful impact (*Egalitarian*, 2025). For the Portugal Students, the challenge was to explore methodologies to estimate the carbon footprint of two Portuguese companies, assessing their environmental impact and proposing actionable strategies for mitigation.

This paper aims to address the lack of studies examining PBL initiatives from the students' perspective, particularly within corporate environments. It analyses the experiences of a student team, focusing on the challenges, difficulties and motivational factors they encountered, as well as how competences acquired throughout their academic journey were applied in practice. The study also highlights the agile project management approach adopted by the team. By offering these insights, this work contributes to a better understanding of how academic skills are integrated into real-world, corporate-driven projects.

2 Project Description

The PBL approach discussed in this paper is implemented during the first semester of the Master's Degree in Industrial Engineering and Management at the University of Minho, specifically in the Integrated Project in Industrial Engineering and Management course. Students at the University of Minho benefit from an institution at the forefront of practical teaching methodologies, having implemented these approaches since 2005 (Lima et al., 2017). This approach immerses students in real-world challenges, offering them the opportunity to tackle practical problems faced by companies across various industries. By working directly within an industrial context, students are encouraged to develop solutions for real-world issues, thereby enhancing both their technical and transversal competences (Lima et al., 2017). The university partners with companies from a wide range of sectors, including construction, energy, textiles and sanitation, providing students with valuable hands-on experience across diverse business environments.

Throughout the project, students benefit from the integration of key concepts from five other courses within the same semester. These courses include Advanced Production Systems Organization, Ergonomics and

Human Factors, Industrial Project Management and Process Modelling and Analysis. Each course plays a crucial role in equipping students to address various aspects of the project, strengthening their practical and theoretical understanding. Teachers responsible for these courses provide continuous support throughout the project's execution, ensuring that students can effectively apply the engineering concepts learned (Lima et al., 2017). The overall project approach encourages the seamless integration of multiple disciplines, fostering collaboration between students, the university and external industry partners. This enriches the students' experience and better prepares them for real-world challenges.

The project is carried out by teams of 7 to 9 students, each assigned to one of the 7 pre-selected companies by the university. These teams collaborate closely with their assigned company, addressing real-world challenges within the company's operational environment (Lima et al., 2017). The problems to be tackled must be simultaneously aligned with the specific needs and priorities of the companies and the boundaries set by the courses' content and learning outcomes. Since this course lasts for only one semester, teams have a four-month window to complete the project, requiring them to manage tasks and deliverables efficiently within a limited timeframe.

To gather relevant data and insights, the team conducts weekly visits to the company, including trips to the shop floor to observe processes and collect firsthand information. During these visits, students meet with company mentors to discuss progress and receive guidance. Additionally, there is a designated day each week solely dedicated to the project, providing time for meetings with teachers and independent work.

The project unfolds in two main phases. Initially, students focus on understanding the company's current state by conducting a thorough diagnostic phase. This involves analyzing processes, identifying inefficiencies and mapping out key challenges within the production system. Once a clear understanding of the existing conditions is established, teams transition to the second phase, developing targeted improvement proposals to address the identified issues (Lima et al., 2017).

Effectively managing a project of this complexity requires a structured approach to ensure teams stay aligned with their objectives and deadlines. Given the short timeframe and the multiple stakeholders involved, students rely on agile project management tools and techniques to plan, coordinate and track progress efficiently.

2.1 Project development

This project was developed in a Portuguese company specialized in off-site bathroom construction, providing faster, simpler and more cost-effective solutions. This company highlighted the need to overcome certain issues within the production system, including unbalanced workstations, a non-linear material flow and poorly defined workstation locations. Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of establishing a line-side delivery system to ensure the efficient and consistent supply of materials to all workstations. Furthermore, integrating human capital into the final solution is crucial to ensure that improvement proposals go beyond the workplace, prioritizing the well-being and engagement of employees. Lastly, as part of the ERASMUS+ EGALITARIAN project, the team was also challenged to quantify the company's carbon footprint, including CO₂ emissions from solid waste. This assessment helps the company better understand its environmental impact and take informed actions to reduce it (Barua et al., 2020).

2.1.1 The need to improve production flow

The current factory layout for manufacturing modular sanitary installations (PODs) faced inefficiencies such as unbalanced workstations, non-linear material flow and poorly defined workstation locations, causing delays, inconsistent material availability and missed production targets (Mahto & Kumar, 2013). Lean methodologies, including takt time, precedence diagrams and line balancing techniques, were applied but proved unfeasible due to space constraints. This restriction led to a collaborative effort with the company to identify simultaneous

tasks inside and outside the POD. The new in-line layout, with continuous flow and a conveyor system, improved synchronization, reduced transport interruptions and waiting times and eliminated forklift use. These changes offered students hands-on experience in Lean Manufacturing and problem-solving.

2.1.2 The need to improve internal logistics activities

The implementation of an efficient internal logistics flow in modular production ensures material availability at the right time without excess stock or waste (Coimbra, 2009). Three replenishment methods were adopted: Mizusumashi (manual cart with 4 or 6 daily cycles), Kanban for bulky and time-sensitive materials, and periodic replenishment for predictable items. Ergonomic analysis confirmed both Mizusumashi cycles as safe (Gotthardt et al., 2019), with the 4-cycle option offering better time efficiency. A visual management system, with boards and luminous signals, enhances stock control, reduces errors and ensures that only necessary materials are transported in each cycle. Despite space constraints caused by the conveyor belt, storage was strategically positioned to optimize flow. This integrated approach balanced material availability, operator safety, and logistical efficiency, meeting the factory's operational needs.

2.1.3 The need to integrate human capital

Organizational systems face constant changes and human capital's adaptability is the key to maintain resilience and achieve goals (Picaró et al., 2016). To understand people as interconnected parts within a work system, a systemic approach was adopted. This approach recognizes the organization as an interdependent system, where human, structural and technological factors directly influence the outcomes, enabling more effective strategic decisions and increasing organizational resilience.

Applying this approach revealed several critical issues. The company has a high turnover rate of 18% and Body Mass Index data highlighted individual health concerns. Moreover, all work instructions, procedures and training are provided solely in Portuguese, creating barriers for non-native speakers. Although the number of accidents is low, external factors were found to contribute to their occurrence.

To address these issues, the team proposed employee recognition and stronger manager-worker relationships to reduce turnover, as well as targeted training to boost satisfaction and retention. Instructions should be provided in a universal language or pictograms, with periodic comprehension assessments. To address Body Mass Index concerns, the canteen should offer tailored meals, supported by awareness campaigns. Additionally, all accident causes, including near misses, should be thoroughly analysed to improve safety.

2.1.4 The need to quantify the carbon footprint

The project addressed the challenge of estimating the company's carbon footprint, a value never previously calculated. This involved a detailed assessment of environmental impacts, covering waste management, energy and water consumption and the development of tools to quantify carbon emissions. Collaboration within the ERASMUS+ EGALITARIAN program, especially with a Brazilian team, was essential to map emission sources across the three scopes and enrich the approach through knowledge exchange.

To estimate the company's CO₂ emissions, emission factors were applied to all activities related to the production, delivery of PODs and treatment of solid waste, considering its end-of-life impact. A carbon footprint calculator was also automated, allowing the company to input data easily and obtain reliable results. Additionally, the tool estimates the number of trees needed to offset emissions and guides the company toward carbon neutrality.

More than a calculation tool, this initiative aims to raise environmental awareness within the organization, supporting informed, sustainable decision-making and concrete steps toward reducing its carbon footprint.

2.2 Project management

Project management is the planning, organization, monitoring and control of all aspects of a project, while motivating all involved to achieve its goals safely, within the agreed schedule, budget and performance criteria (IPMA (International Project Management Association), 2006). It encompasses various methodologies, each designed to enhance efficiency and structure within a project. Among these, the Project Model Canvas is a project management tool that provides a comprehensive overview of all key aspects, including objectives, stakeholders and project stages. Inspired by the Business Model Generation, it simplifies project planning by using a visual and intuitive approach, reducing bureaucracy and facilitating quick decision-making (Silva & Cardoso, 2019).

The Project Model Canvas served as a true guiding thread for the team, providing a clear and structured framework for the project's development. Its centralized visualization made it easier to identify potential limitations and challenges, enabling a more proactive and efficient management approach. As a result, the team remained aligned and adapted to project needs and made more informed decisions throughout the process.

As the project progressed, it became clear that the tool needed adjustments to align with the emerging objectives. Consequently, it was necessary to make some changes to the initial version of this document in order to more accurately reflect the current reality of the project. One critical aspect that was initially overlooked but proved to be essential was the potential interruption of production at the factory. This unexpected constraint caused significant delays, highlighting the importance of anticipating such risks from the early planning stages to mitigate their impact and ensure better timeline management.

The SCRUM framework is widely recognized as one of the most implemented approaches within agile project management (Lei et al., 2017). This methodology supports collaborative efforts among team members by dividing their work into manageable tasks that are designed to be completed during fixed-length cycles known as "sprints" (Hidalgo, 2019). Through regular meetings, the team monitors their progress and adjusts plans as necessary, enabling the incremental development of products.

During the project's development, SCRUM artifacts were implemented to ensure efficient management aligned with its objectives. Defining roles was crucial to the process's success: the Product Owners represented the company's interests, the SCRUM Master facilitated the workflow and helped overcome obstacles and the development team executed tasks, turning ideas into results. At the end of each sprint, a Sprint Review Meeting was held to assess completed work and adjust future plans.

To provide clear progress tracking, the team implemented a Kanban Board, enabling the visualization of ongoing, completed and pending tasks, which facilitates continuous monitoring and efficient project management. Weekly sprints were conducted, starting with Sprint Planning Meetings to define tasks, assign responsibilities and estimate effort using the Planning Poker technique. Additionally, in Daily Scrums, the team communicates progress and upcoming tasks, allowing the SCRUM Master to update the Kanban Board as work progresses.

Leveraging the Kanban Board, the team also developed a Burndown Chart to monitor task completion rates and adjust actions as needed, ensuring the project remains on schedule. These artifacts not only structured the workflow but also provided flexibility and visibility, allowing the team to adapt to emerging challenges effectively.

3 What about the experience?

The participation in this project represented a significant milestone for our team, marking our first direct experience with the industry. Throughout the project, we faced a variety of challenges that tested our ability to adapt, collaborate and find innovative solutions under real-world constraints. This experience enriched our academic journey and contributed significantly to our professional and personal development.

3.1 Understanding each other

Right from the beginning, we recognised the importance of understanding the individual characteristics of each team member, which led us to conduct personality and work-style assessments before starting the project. This initiative allowed us to anticipate potential dynamics and make the most of each member's strengths, ensuring a productive and collaborative environment. In this initial phase, we used the MBTI (Myers-Briggs Type Indicator) test to identify the main personality types within the group, which included Analysts, Sentinels, Diplomats and Explorers. This diversity was key to balancing perspectives and working styles. Additionally, the Belbin Team Roles test helped us understand how each person naturally contributes to a team setting, identifying profiles such as Monitor Evaluator, Implementer and Teamworker. These tools enabled us to strategically form subgroups with complementary strengths. A clear example was the subgroup formed by three team members with highly analytical, structured and leadership-oriented profiles, combining a focus on strategic vision, organization and decision-making under pressure. In this trio, their Belbin profiles (Completer Finisher, Implementer and Monitor Evaluator) worked in perfect synergy, ensuring that ideas were implemented efficiently, with rigorous quality control and constant monitoring of project objectives. This approach directly impacted the success and resilience of the project, especially in high-pressure situations. This allowed the members to know each other better, which naturally strengthened trust, communication and group cohesion. This familiarity made it easier to anticipate reactions, distribute tasks intuitively and maintain a positive and highly supportive working atmosphere. It allowed us to form not just a good team, but an exceptional one, where collaboration was seamless and motivation came naturally.

3.2 Dealing with unexpected events

One of the most demanding moments occurred when the company shifted its focus to a different project, leading to a temporary halt in production. At that point, our team had already conducted a thorough diagnostic analysis, only to realise that we had to restart this phase within a much shorter timeframe. This imposed an additional layer of complexity, requiring us to be more agile, prioritize tasks effectively and make data-driven decisions more efficiently. However, what could have been a setback was transformed into a key moment of growth thanks to our structured teamwork, deep knowledge of one another's working styles and the resilience we had developed. We quickly reorganised ourselves, relying on the strengths of each profile and using our well-established subgroups to respond rapidly and effectively. Therefore, this situation ultimately turned into an opportunity to refine our analytical skills, enhance our problem-solving abilities and improve our ability to work under pressure.

Another significant challenge arose when our initial company mentor left the organization midway through the project. The transition to a new mentor presented some initial difficulties, as we had to quickly adapt to a different leadership style and reestablish a working dynamic. Nevertheless, we were able to navigate the transition effectively, ensuring the project moved forward with clarity and purpose. We were fortunate to receive consistent support, not only from our new mentor, who quickly integrated into the project and offered valuable guidance, but also from the company itself. Their ongoing encouragement and the clear recognition of the value of our work played a fundamental role in our motivation. Knowing that our efforts were appreciated and that our contributions had a real impact was incredibly rewarding. This sense of acknowledgement became

a driving force that pushed us to improve and give our very best continuously. This experience was not only a test of our adaptability and resilience, but also a powerful reminder of the importance of supportive leadership and a positive organizational culture in overcoming challenges.

Moreover, our collaboration with a specialized organization in continuous improvement provided valuable insights into efficiency and innovation approaches. The exchange of knowledge with industry professionals allowed us to broaden our understanding of the problem from a new perspective, adding value to our work and strengthening our proposed solutions.

3.3 International collaboration

The integration of the ERASMUS+ Egalitarian project was a transformative experience for our team, particularly due to its focus on sustainability. A key contribution was the calculation of the company's carbon footprint, which allowed us to identify areas for improvement and implement more environmentally conscious practices. This analysis not only aligned with our technical goals but also deepened our understanding of sustainable engineering. This multicultural and interdisciplinary collaboration allowed for a broader perspective, integrating diverse approaches to enhance both efficiency and sustainability. The exchange of knowledge and methodologies from different academic backgrounds contributed to the development of more inclusive, adaptable and socially responsible engineering solutions. Beyond the technical benefits, participating in an ERASMUS+ project brought invaluable advantages. It facilitated knowledge exchange with international teams, exposing us to diverse perspectives and innovative approaches. This collaboration strengthened our teamwork, communication and adaptability, as we worked to align Egalitarian principles with our project goals. Furthermore, the experience provided personal and professional growth opportunities for team members, fostering a greater awareness of the social and environmental impacts of engineering. By integrating Egalitarian into our work, we developed solutions that were efficient and aligned with sustainability principles and global responsibility.

3.4 Peer feedback

Beyond the technical and managerial aspects, this project also emphasized the importance of teamwork and self-assessment. Throughout the semester, our team underwent two formal evaluation moments, where we not only received feedback from our professors but also engaged in a peer assessment process. Each member was required to anonymously evaluate contributions, dynamics and overall team performance. The unanimous assignment of equal workload points among all members was a testament to our team's balanced effort distribution and strong collaborative spirit. The feedback we exchanged was overwhelmingly positive, with comments highlighting mutual support, seamless task allocation and a proactive attitude in achieving project goals. Responses emphasized our ability to maintain a constructive working environment, effectively manage conflicts and foster motivation among team members. In particular, one of the responses in the team dynamics evaluation stood out:

"The division of tasks among the team members according to their skills greatly helped the project's development. Everyone adhered to deadlines, ensuring the team met its objectives. Knowing each other well facilitated communication and problem-solving, allowing us to reach agreements quickly by actively listening to each other. Additionally, we always took the opportunity to engage in team-building moments to strengthen relationships and better handle the challenges we encountered." (Team member feedback)

This feedback encapsulates one of the great strengths of our team: our ability to anticipate, adapt and support one another. Because we invested early in understanding how we work, how we think and how we respond under pressure, even the most complex situations were faced with confidence. Problems arose, as they do in

any project, but our cohesion, mutual trust and respect made problem-solving natural and efficient. Difficulties became opportunities to learn, test our resilience and strengthen our collaborative bond.

3.5 Learning results – beyond content

Looking forward, the learnings from this project are highly transferable to other professional and academic contexts. We now understand that successful teamwork is not only about technical competence but also about knowing how to manage different personalities, leadership styles and communication needs. We have learned that adaptability, empathy and a well-balanced distribution of responsibilities, based on each member's natural skills, are key for any team's success. In future projects, we'll carry this experience forward, ensuring that we start by building a solid team foundation, valuing diversity and being aware that not everyone responds in the same way to challenges, leadership or pressure. This awareness will allow us to create even stronger, more resilient and efficient teams, capable of thriving in increasingly complex and multicultural professional environments.

Overall, this project was an invaluable learning experience, offering us a realistic glimpse into industry operations while reinforcing the importance of teamwork, adaptability and continuous learning. The challenges we faced were not mere obstacles but stepping stones – powerful moments of transformation that allowed us to grow both as individuals and as a truly exceptional team. The resilience, collaboration and strategy we demonstrated here will undoubtedly serve as a strong foundation for our future careers, wherever they may lead.

4 Concluding Remarks

This project was more than just an academic exercise; it was an immersive experience in the professional world, where theory and practice converged in a dynamic and challenging way. Rooted in the PBL approach, this initiative provided a hands-on environment where students tackled real-world challenges in collaboration with a company. From the initial contact to the final delivery, every stage was an opportunity for intense learning, filled with challenges, discoveries and personal growth.

Throughout this journey, it became clear that the success of a project is not solely based on technical knowledge but also on adaptability, effective communication and teamwork. Interacting with industry professionals provided us with a privileged insight into market demands, highlighting the importance of skills such as flexibility, problem-solving and expectation management.

Facing unexpected difficulties was part of the process and became one of the greatest sources of learning. The need to align innovative solutions with the company's real needs pushed us to think strategically, experiment different approaches and learn from our mistakes.

Beyond the academic impact, this project reinforced the relevance of collaboration between universities and companies, demonstrating how these partnerships can generate mutual benefits. Students gain valuable practical experience for their future careers, while companies receive creative solutions and fresh perspectives on their challenges.

More than just a curricular assignment, this experience was a concrete step in shaping our professional identity. The bridge between higher education and the job market must continue to be strengthened, as it is through real-world challenges that the professionals of the future are forged.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia within the R&D Unit Project Scope UID/00319/Centro ALGORITMI (ALGORITMI/UM).

This work was partially developed in the context of project 2023-1-DK01-KA220-HED-00165709, “EGALITARIAN - Education, Digitalisation and Collaboration for Sustainability,” which has been funded with support from the European Commission. This publication reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

References

- Alves, A. C., Sousa, R. M., Fernandes, S., Cardoso, E., Carvalho, M. A., Figueiredo, J., & Pereira, R. M. S. (2016). Teacher's experiences in PBL: implications for practice. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 41(2), 123–141. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2015.1023782>
- Barua, S., Sarigamala, K., Boruah, D., Ramaswamy, A. P., & Poyyamoli, G. (2020). Carbon Footprint Assessment and Mitigation Strategies for Sustainable Development. *Strategic Planning for Energy and the Environment*, 2, 55.
- Coimbra, E. A. (2009). *Total Flow Management: Achieving Excellence with Kaizen and Lean Supply Chains* (1st Edition). Kaizen Institute.
- Egalitarian. (2025). <https://egalitarian.eu/>
- Freeman, S., Eddy, S. L., McDonough, M., Smith, M. K., Okoroafor, N., Jordt, H., & Wenderoth, M. P. (2014). Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 111(23), 8410–8415. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1319030111>
- Gotthardt, S., Hulla, M., Eder, M., Karre, H., & Ramsauer, C. (2019). Digitalized milk-run system for a learning factory assembly line. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 31, 175–179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2019.03.028>
- Habók, A., & Nagy, J. (2016). In-service teachers' perceptions of project-based learning. *SpringerPlus*, 5(1), 83. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40064-016-1725-4>
- Han, S., Yalvac, B., Capraro, M. M., & Capraro, R. M. (2015). In-service teachers' implementation and understanding of STEM project based learning. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 11(1), 63–76. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eurasia.2015.1306a>
- Hidalgo, E. S. (2019). Adapting the scrum framework for agile project management in science: case study of a distributed research initiative. *Heliyon*, 5(3), e01447. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e01447>
- IPMA (International Project Management Association). (2006). *ICB - IPMA Competence Baseline, Version 3.0* (G. Caupin, H. Knoepfel, G. Koch, K. Pannbäcker, F. Pérez-Polo, & C. Seabury, Eds.). International Project Management Association.
- Jaca, C., Ormazabal, M., Arizmendi, M., & Blanco, C. (2021, June). Project-Based Learning Implementation. Collaboration between University and Industry. *Proceedings of the 17th International CDIO Conference*.
- Jaroenkhasemmesuk, C., Lima, R. M., Horgan, K., Mesquita, D., & Supeekit, T. (2023). Active Learning in Engineering Education: Case Study in Mechanics for Engineering. *Advances in Transdisciplinary Engineering*, 41, 633–642. <https://doi.org/10.3233/ATDE230659>
- Lei, H., Ganjeizadeh, F., Jayachandran, P. K., & Ozcan, P. (2017). A statistical analysis of the effects of Scrum and Kanban on software development projects. *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, 43, 59–67. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcim.2015.12.001>
- Lima, R. M., Dinis-Carvalho, J., Sousa, R., Alves, A., Moreira, F., Fernandes, S., & Mesquita, D. (2017). *Ten Years of Project-Based Learning (PBL) in Industrial Engineering and Management at the University of Minho* (pp. 33–51). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6300-905-8_3
- Lima, R. M., Dinis-Carvalho, J., Sousa, R. M., Arezes, P., & Mesquita, D. (2017). Development of competences while solving real industrial interdisciplinary problems: A successful cooperation with industry. *Production*, 27. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0103-6513.230016>
- Mahto, D. G., & Kumar, N. (2013). *Productivity Improvement Through Process Analysis for Optimizing Assembly Line in Packaging Industries*. <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=2770413>
- Major, J., & Kirn, A. (2016, June 26). Engineering Design Self-Efficacy and Project-Based Learning: How Does Active Learning Influence Student Attitudes and Beliefs? *2016 ASEE Annual Conference & Exposition Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.18260/p.26637>
- Major, J., & Kirn, A. (2017). Engineering Identity and Project-Based Learning: How Does Active Learning Develop Student Engineering Identity? *2017 ASEE Annual Conference & Exposition Proceedings*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.18260/1-2--28255>
- Picaró, J., Coelho, M. S., & Silva, J. N. (2016). *O Papel dos Recursos Humanos na Gestão da Mudança. O Caso do Regimento de Artilharia Antiaérea Nº1 (Raa1)* (Issue 11).
- Silva, H., & Cardoso, A. (2019). Research Project Model Canvas. *Computer Science and Information Technology*, 7(3), 55–64. <https://doi.org/10.13189/csit.2019.070301>
- Theobald, E. J., Hill, M. J., Tran, E., Agrawal, S., Arroyo, E. N., Behling, S., Chambwe, N., Cintrón, D. L., Cooper, J. D., Dunster, G., Grummer, J. A., Hennessey, K., Hsiao, J., Iranon, N., Jones, L., Jordt, H., Keller, M., Lacey, M. E., Littlefield, C. E., ... Freeman, S. (2020). Active learning narrows achievement gaps for underrepresented students in undergraduate science, technology, engineering, and math. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117(12), 6476–6483. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1916903117>